

Validation of the Mie Theory for Rain Attenuation at 72 and 84 GHz

Eugene Hong, Steven Lane, and David Murrell
 Space Vehicles Directorate
 Air Force Research Laboratory
 Kirtland AFB, NM 87117, USA
 eugene.hong.ctr@us.af.mil

Christos Christodoulou
 Electrical and Computer Engineering Department
 University of New Mexico
 Albuquerque, NM 87131, USA

I. INTRODUCTION

The utilization of radio frequency (RF) spectrum resources for satellite communication has developed towards shorter wavelengths due to the demand for higher data transmission capacity. At extremely high frequency (EHF, or millimeter wave, 30-300 GHz) bands, we expect to achieve gigabit per second rates for space-to-ground communication with a smaller payload and antenna relative to lower frequencies [1]. While the Q-band (33-50 GHz), which is the lowest frequency band in EHF, has started to provide some operational capabilities, the next higher frequency, V-band (40-75 GHz), and W-band (75-110 GHz) are also being considered for future satellite communication needs [2]. However, before we can move into the W and V frequency bands, we must have a better understanding of the effects imparted by the atmospheric channel.

Among the well-known causes of attenuation and scattering in the atmosphere, rain is the dominant cause at W/V-band. At these frequencies, the wavelength is comparable to the size of raindrops. Therefore, validation of rain attenuation and scattering models for W/V-band is a prerequisite for any operational system development. In this paper, we focus on validating the Mie theory for rain attenuation at 72 and 84 GHz [3]. We compare model predictions under various parameters such as complex index of refraction models and raindrop size distribution (i.e., DSD) models to experimental data. The data is collected from our outdoor test range, which is referred to as the W/V-band Terrestrial Link Experiment (WTLE).

II. THEORY

The Mie theory solves Maxwell's equations for the scattering of electromagnetic plane waves by a spherical-shaped particle with spherical Bessel functions. Mie coefficients are obtained from the boundary conditions at the surface of the scattering particle, and the complex index of refraction of the particle. Using the Mie coefficients and the Poynting vector law, extinction and scattering cross sections are calculated from:

$$\sigma_{ext} = \frac{2\pi}{k_m^2} \text{Re} \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} (2l+1)(a_l + b_l), \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_{sct} = \frac{2\pi}{k_m^2} \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} (2l+1)(|a_l|^2 + |b_l|^2), \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_{abs} = \sigma_{ext} - \sigma_{sct}, \quad (3)$$

where k_m is the wavenumber of an incident wave in the transmission medium, a_l and b_l are l^{th} order Mie coefficients, and σ_{ext} , σ_{sct} , and σ_{abs} are extinction, scattering, and absorption cross sections, respectively [4].

With the cross sections from the Mie theory, rain attenuation is obtained. The specific rain attenuation, A (dB/km), is calculated from:

$$A \left(\frac{\text{dB}}{\text{km}} \right) = 0.4343 \int_0^{\infty} n(r, R) \cdot \sigma_{ext}(r) dr, \quad (4)$$

where r (mm) is the radius of the raindrop, R (mm/hr) is the rain rate, σ_{ext} (cm^2) is the extinction cross section, and $n(r, R)$ ($\text{m}^{-3}\text{mm}^{-1}$) is the DSD value at the corresponding rain rate and drop size, which can be chosen from the known models or from disdrometer measurements [5]. By using the extinction cross section, we include both scattering and absorption complex index effects from rain droplets.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

WTLE is a ground-based W/V-band link experiment that was designed to study propagation effects and enable correlation to meteorological parameters and conditions. WTLE is located in Albuquerque, New Mexico, with the transmitter located at the top of Sandia Mountain. The transmitter transmits vertically and horizontally polarized unmodulated signals at 72 and 84 GHz. The companion receiver is located at the University of New Mexico's Configurable Space Microsystems Innovations and Applications Center (COSMIAC), which is near the Albuquerque International Sunport (i.e., airport). This receiver continuously monitors the amplitude, phase and relative polarization of the transmitted signals. The total travel distance between the transmitter and the receiver is about 23.6 km, which includes about 1.7 km of elevation change.

A disdrometer is located at the receiver. The disdrometer measures the number of raindrops in 22 size classes and 20 velocity classes every minute. Fig. 1 shows DSD data

from October 2015. WTLE started operation in mid-September 2015. It is expected to collect data until the end of 2017.

Fig. 1. Raindrop size distribution from October 2015.

From WTLE, we expect to gather data under various meteorological conditions due to the dynamic weather conditions in Albuquerque over all seasons, including summer monsoon season.

IV. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

We present the extinction cross section, σ_{ext} , from the Mie theory at 72 GHz with Segelstein's complex index of refraction values [6] as a function of the raindrop size in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Extinction cross section as a function of raindrop size at 72 GHz with Segelstein's complex index of refraction values.

We plan to develop a comparison between DSD models and disdrometer measurements. Among DSD models that we plan to examine, we will find a model that represents the measurements best.

Lastly, we plan to compare the predicted total rain attenuation over the propagation path computed with (4) to measured attenuation data. Since the disdrometer is located at the receiver, the precise rain rate is only available at the

receiver. Therefore, we plan to use the digital precipitation rate data, which is obtained from the Next Generation Weather Radar (NEXRAD) system, provided by National Climatic Data Center (i.e. NCDC), to obtain the estimated rain rate over the propagation path. Fig. 3 illustrates such a measurement for the vertically polarized 72 GHz signal over a 24-hour period. Rain attenuation is estimated by subtracting the clear-day path attenuation.

Fig. 3. Rain attenuation measurement for 72 GHz, vertically polarized signal on October 19th 2015.

V. SUMMARY

This paper presents the Mie theory for propagation loss resulting from atmosphere scattering and absorption for W/V frequency bands. The theory will be validated using experiment data collected on a 23-km test and measurement range, which is instrumented with an unmodulated transmitter, a receiver, and several meteorology instruments. This research is crucial for understanding signal propagation phenomena and enabling the utilization of the W/V-bands for satellite communication.

REFERENCES

- [1] E. Cianca, T. Rossi, A. Yahalom, Y. Pinhasi, J. Farserotu, and C. Sacchi, "EHF for satellite communications: The new broadband frontier", *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 99, no. 11, pp. 1858–1881, Nov. 2011.
- [2] P. Kangaslahti, T. Gaier, M. Seiffert, S. Weinreb, D. Harding, D. Dawson, M. Soria, C. Lawrence, B. Hooberman, and A. Miller, "Planar polarimetry receivers for large imaging arrays at Q-band", *Microwave Symposium Digest, 2006. IEEE MTT-S International*, pp. 89–92, 11–16 June 2006
- [3] G. Mie, "Beiträge zur optik trüber medien, speziell kolloidaler metallösungen", *Annalen der Physik*, vol. 330, no. 3, pp. 377–445, 1908.
- [4] H. C. van de Hulst, "Light scattering by small particles", *John Wiley and Sons*, 1957.
- [5] R. R. Rogers, "Statistical rainstorm models: Their theoretical and physical foundations", *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 24, no. 4, pp. 547–566, July 1976.
- [6] D. J. Segelstein, "The complex refractive index of water", M.S. Thesis, Department of Physics, University of Missouri-Kansas City, 1981.